

Toxic Action of Grapes towards Dogs

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Summary:

Ingestion of *Uva Vitis vinifera* L. has been reported to cause acute kidney injury (AKI) in dogs, with a clinical picture dominated by early gastrointestinal signs and rapidly developing uremia, ataxia, and possible neurological damage.

This study aims to identify the active components present in grapes that can cause such symptoms in dogs.

Introduction:

Since 1998, numerous cases have been published of dogs developing acute kidney injury (AKI) after ingesting *Vitis vinifera* L grapes. The chemical compound and its mechanism of toxicity is still unknown. Hypotheses include contamination of fruits with mycotoxins, heavy metals or pesticides, excess vitamin D, [1] tannin intolerance or excessive monosaccharide ingestion, [2] hypovolemic shock and renal ischemia. [3] The exact amount of ingested fruit needed to cause harm is not known and estimates are based on clinical cases. [3], [4], [5] The lowest dose reported to cause AKI is 19.6 g/kg of body weight for grapes and 2.8 g/kg for raisins. [4]

Literature survey:

This study aims to compare the phytocomplex of grape extracts *Vitis vinifera* L. with other potentially harmless or even beneficial fruits for dogs such as blueberries *Vaccinium myrtillus* L. and raspberries *Rubus idaeus* L. to find the toxic discriminant.

From the investigation of the *Vitis vinifera* L. phytocomplex it can be seen that Phenols, Terpenoids, Anthocyanins, Reducing sugar and Quinones are present in all grape species [6].

While in the analyzes conducted on *Rubus idaeus* L. and *Vaccinium myrtillus* L. the Quinones component is missing or not significantly detected [7], [8].

Quinones represent a class of toxicological intermediates that can create a variety of hazardous effects in vivo, including acute cytotoxicity, immunotoxicity, and carcinogenesis.

From a chemical point of view, quinones are a class of organic compounds formally derived from aromatic compounds in which an even number of -CH= groups is replaced by as many -C(=O)- groups, with the necessary rearrangements of the double bonds and individual elements of the structure so as to present the structure of a fully conjugated cyclic diketone.

The mechanisms by which quinones cause these effects can be quite complex. Quinones are Michael acceptors and cellular damage can occur through alkylation of crucial cellular proteins and/or DNA. Alternatively, quinones are highly redox active molecules that can recycle the redox cycle with their semiquinone radicals, leading to the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), including superoxide, hydrogen peroxide, and ultimately the hydroxyl radical. ROS production can cause severe oxidative stress within cells through the formation of oxidized cellular macromolecules, including lipids, proteins, and DNA [9].

Phytochemical comparison: *Vitis Vinifera*, *Vaccinium myrtillus*, *Rubus idaeus* L.

Composed	Grape (<i>Vitis vinifera</i> L.)	Blueberry <i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i> L.	Raspberry <i>Rubus idaeus</i> L.
Phenols	+	+	+
Quinones	+	-	-
Terpenoids	+	+	+
Anthocyanins	+	+	+

Conclusions:

Based on the data presented in this study, the presence of quinones in the phytochemical complex which would cause cellular damage to the kidney and neurological system seems to appear evident as the triggering cause of the toxicity of grapes towards dogs.

These studies require additional investigation of an experimental toxicological nature.

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9. Role of quinones in toxicology

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